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NOMINATIVE DETERMINISM AND IMMIGRANT IDENTITY: AN EXPLORATION OF *THE NAMESAKE*

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Abstract: *This paper is an exploring tour through Jhumpa Lahiri's novel The Namesake to expose the tug of war between two worlds, one the east and the other the west. The complicated, multicultural identity of an individual nag the person especially for the name tag stuck upon him. Gogol's rather wacky name irks him. It is with this effect of a name that Gogol attempts to live. Nominative determinism comes to play a role in the novel. Gogol sees his name as both the cause and the symbol of the way he feels as an Indian-American, caught between the Bengali heritage of his parents and the American culture he lives in. Together with it, the condition of the mother who feels everything strange in a foreign land is also made a matter of study. The study upon the equipage of the novel gets into the trapped identity of the Diaspora community in general.*

Key Words: Determinism, Nominative Determinism, Immigrant Identity, *The Namesake*

1. Introduction

The Namesake is the first novel written by Jhumpa Lahiri. The plot moves between events in Calcutta, Boston, and New York City to expose the varied cultural, social, and psychological nuances involved with each one of them. Lahiri's elegantly measured narrative voice, which is gentle, wise, and unassuming, weaves the common thread for the entire story. The elegance and poise of the writer are uncommon and accolades get accumulated to her credit.

In 2003, Lahiri published *The Namesake*. The story spans over thirty years in the life of the Ganguli family. The Calcutta-born parents immigrate as young adults to the United States where their children, Gogol and Sonia, grow up experiencing the constant generational and cultural gap with their parents. New to America, Ashima struggles

through language and cultural barriers as well as her fears as she delivers her first child alone. As per the Bengali tradition, the child is to be named by the eldest member of the family. Thus they wait for Ashima's grandmother's letter from Calcutta which never arrives. Bengali culture calls for a child to have two names, a pet name to be called by family, and a good name to be used in public. Ashoke suggests the name of Gogol, in honor of the famous Ukrainian author Nikolai Gogol, to be the baby's pet name, and they use this name on the birth certificate. Entering kindergarten, the Gangulis inform their son that he will be known as Nikhil at school. But Gogol resists the name and sticks on to his pet name. It was thus Gogol came to be called so even at school. But by the time he turns 14, he starts to hate the name for its oddness. Gogol wants himself to be a pure American instead of being true to his lineage.

The story goes on to explain Gogol's engagements and his final acceptance of the name.

2. The Pain of Labor in America

Quite literally Ashima suffers labor pain while being in America. In the labor room, she thinks that it is the first time she is sleeping alone, surrounded only by strangers. But a twitch from the baby reminds her that she is, technically speaking, not alone. If she was in India, Ashima would have gone to her parents, retreating briefly to childhood. Dr. Ashley who supervises Ashima says, "Everything is looking perfectly normal. But nothing feels normal to Ashima. For the past eighteen months, ever since she has arrived in Cambridge, nothing has felt normal at all." (5). The consequence of making motherhood in a foreign land is more painful than the labor pain that it is happening so far from home, unmonitored by those she loved. For Ashima, without a single grandparent or parent or uncle or aunt by her side, the baby's birth seems to become only half true. The Nandis in Cambridge and Dr. Gupta, despite their love and care, are only substitutes for the people who really ought to be surrounding them. Ashima even feels pity for the child that she has never known of a person entering the world so alone, so deprived. During Gogol's annaprasam (rice ceremony), Ashima's eyes fill with tears as Gogol's mouth eagerly invites the spoon. She cannot help wishing her brother were there to feed him, her parents to bless him with their hands on his head.

In *The Namesake*, Ashima does not prefer to get pregnant in the USA. After giving birth to Gogol, though not pregnant, she realizes that being a foreigner is a sort of lifelong pregnancy. Everyone treats her like a stranger in America. Lahiri says, "For being a foreigner, Ashima is beginning to realize, is a sort of lifelong pregnancy- a perpetual wait, a

constant burden, a continuous feeling out of sorts."(49) For her it is an ongoing responsibility. And what she gets from the strangers is the same combination of pity and respect. Ashima says that after twenty years in America, she still cannot bring herself to refer to Pemberton Road as home. The writer has very well interiorized the pain of the diaspora into the figure of Ashima.

Articulations of diaspora frequently and consistently maintain that for a specific group to be considered diasporic, there should be a physical dispersal from an original center to two or more peripheral foreign regions as well as the retention of collective memory or myth about the original homeland which in most cases would result in a physical return. This perfectly happens for Ashima. Ashima indirectly becomes the symbol of Lahiri's mother. Lahiri was born in London, the daughter of Indian immigrants from the state of West Bengal. Her family moved to the United States when she was two. Lahiri grew up in Kingston, Rhode Island, where her father Amar Lahiri worked as a librarian at the University of Rhode Island. Lahiri's mother wanted her children to grow up knowing their Bengali heritage, and her family often visited relatives in Calcutta. Ashima in the story teaches Gogol Tagore's poems. But when she closes her eyes it never fails to unsettle her that the children sound just like Americans. Children prefer the Western ways, slices of cheese, mayonnaise, tuna fish, and hot dogs. Yet the parents insist that they go for a Kathakali dance performance or sitar recital so that they would get acquainted at least in part with the language and culture of Bengal.

The fear of their children getting dislocated is a constant disturbing thought for the parents. Gogol is the quintessential first-generation American son. He never speaks to his parents in Bengali, and he's embarrassed by

their idiosyncrasies. For the sake of Gogol and Sonia, they celebrate, with progressively increasing fanfare, the birth of Christ, an event the children look forward to far more than the worship of Durga and Saraswati. Like immigrants of other communication, Ashima and Ashoke too make their circle of Bengali acquaintances. They all become friends only for the reason that “they all come from Calcutta”. (38) Robert Cohen rightly remarks “a member’s adherence to a diasporic community is demonstrated by an acceptance of an inescapable link with their past migration history” (Cohen:ix:1997). These Bengali families celebrate these different customs and ceremonies like marriages, death, childbirth, festivals, etc together. They celebrate these as per Bengali customs, wearing their best traditional attire, thus trying to preserve their culture in a new land.

The novel shows how the immigrants face cultural dilemmas in the foreign system. Lahiri shows that the immigrants in their enthusiasm to stick to their own cultural beliefs and customs gradually imbibe the cultural ways of the host country too. Their own children groomed to be bilingual and bicultural face cultural dilemmas and displacement more. The novel examines how the first and second generations are caught between two conflicting cultures with their religio-socio differences.

3. The Name Game in *The Namesake*

Gogol and Sonia are the representatives of the second class of generation in the story. Gogol’s only ally is Sonia. From time to time they privately admit to excruciating cravings, for hamburgers or a slice of pepperoni pizza, or a cold glass of milk. The travel to their homeland is travail for the children. Returning from Delhi to Calcutta, they have constipation followed by the opposite. It is with Gogol the pain of a dislocated name comes to

disturb. Instances of nominative determinist tension seem to outgrip the boy in America.

Nominative determinism is the theory that a person's name can have a significant role in determining key aspects of a job, profession, or even character. That the name may decide the entire personality associated with the bearer. The term nominative determinism had its origin in the 'Feedback' column of the British popular science magazine *New Scientist* in 1994. In 2002, nominative determinism became a serious study in its own right, with the publication of a paper in the *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* entitled 'Why Susie Sells Seashells by the Seashore: Implicit Egotism and Major Life Decisions. The theory when applied to Lahiri’s story has got a lot of significance. Gogol’s entire dislocation happens not because of his Bengali lineage but because of the weight (lessness) of the name that he carries.

As a young boy, Gogol does not mind his name. Then one day the peculiarity of his name becomes apparent. One day the students are taken to a graveyard as part of a school project. All of them look for similar names on the graves. But Gogol found no name to match his. Gogol has come to hate questions about his name and hates having constantly to explain. He even hates signing his name at the bottom of his drawings in art class. He hates that his name is both absurd and obscure, nothing to do with who he is, that it is neither Indian nor American but of all things Russian. The name has a history behind it. Gogol’s father, Ashoke had a close encounter with death as a young man when he survived a train crash in his native India. On the train, he happened to be reading a book by his favorite author, Nikolai Gogol. So it is that years later when he is living in America with his new wife, Ashima, he decides to give their newborn son the pet name “Gogol.” It soon

becomes his given name, but for years little Gogol is unaware of the significance behind it. Gogol wants to at least shorten the name. But Gogol already short and catchy resists mutation. He cannot even imagine telling a girl, “Hi, it’s Gogol” under any potential romantic circumstance. “Gogol sounds ludicrous to his ears, lacking dignity or gravity.” (96) Once Gogol introduces himself to a girl as Nikhil. The name has got a meaning, he who is entire, encompassing all. With the change of name, he is confident about kissing the girl. “He kissed her. But he does not believe that it was Gogol who had kissed Kim.” (96) The idea to change his name had first occurred to him while being at a dentist’s. He saw an article in the *Reader’s Digest* with the title “Second Baptisms”. In the court the only reason that Gogol can think of changing the name is that “I hate the name Gogol. I have always hated it.” (102) And now that he is Nikhil it is easier to ignore his parents for they had said, to them Gogol will never be anyone but Gogol. The name was a constant disturbance for him that he changed it. This agitation associated with the name is the author’s own experience getting portrayed. Lahiri was born Nilanjana Sudeshna. When she began kindergarten in Kingston, Rhode Island, her teacher decided to call her by her pet name, Jhumpa, because it was easier to pronounce than her proper name. Lahiri recalled that she always felt so embarrassed by her name. Lahiri’s ambivalence over her identity was the inspiration for the ambivalence of Gogol over his unusual name.

Gogol comes to regret the change of name only at the cost of a loss. It is with the death of his father that Gogol realizes the warmth associated with the name. Gogol, the prodigal son, leaves his swanky, independent life in New York City to help, flying to Cleveland to claim the body and pack up his father’s temporary apartment. “Thinking of his

father living here, alone these past three months, he feels the first threat of tears, but he knows that his father did not mind, that he was not offended by such things.” (174) In the apartment, Gogol finds sneakers, flip-flops, a photo of the family on the refrigerator, four plates, two mugs, four glasses, some tea and sugar, and rice. He cancels the utilities, calls his father’s workplace and returns the leased car. These mundane activities are, for Gogol, at once therapeutic. After packing up all of his father’s belongings, he lies on the couch to sleep, and unable to do so thinks about what happened to his father. “Gogol imagines his father by the door, bending over to tie his shoelaces for the last time. Putting on his coat and scarf and driving to the hospital. Stopping at a traffic light, listening to the weather report on the radio, the thought of death absent from his mind.” (178) For the first time ever in his life Gogol understands the significance of his name. Gogol comes to accept his name and picks up a collection of the Russian author's stories that his father had given him as a birthday present many years ago.

It is only with the acceptance of his name that Gogol comes to peace of mind. The concept of a perfect name for himself is abandoned for his good. Gogol finally proclaims, “There is no such thing as a perfect name.” (245) And Lahiri fills the rest that there is only one thing as the acceptance of one’s name.

4. Conclusion

The Namesake is so refreshing with its open sensuality and hidden complexity. It is more than a book about a name. It is about finding identity in a country that will treat you as an alien even if you were born there. This alienation would be worsened if the person is dissatisfied with his own received identity as what had happened with

Gogol. The first thing to be done is to get acquainted with your name and feel yourself being in that name. In this context, many questions arise as to why people of famous personalities change their names. There is yet another section for discussion.

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SYNODALITY IN THE SYRO MALANKARA CATHOLIC CHURCH:

A HISTORICAL AND PASTORAL APPROACH

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Abstract: Synodality represents the main road for the Church, called to renew herself under the action of the Spirit and by listening to the Word. Alone we can do so little; Together, we can do so much. Holy Father Pope Francis invites each of us to think, suggest, and work together to achieve or fulfill the Synodal nature of the Church. Synodality is not a new concept; instead, it's an invitation to re-discover the practice of the early Church.

Key Words: Synodality, Syro-Malankara Catholic Church, Pastoral Approach

1. Introduction

Synodality represents the main road for the Church, called to renew herself under the action of the Spirit and by listening to the Word. Alone we can do so little; Together, we can do so much. Holy Father Pope Francis invites each of us to think, suggest, and work together to achieve or fulfill the synodal nature of the Church. Synodality is not a new concept; instead, it's an invitation to re-discover the practice of the early Church.

Concepts like lay participation, collegiality, and the democratic system evolved in different ways in the eastern and western Church. "In the western churches, the nature and growth of the church had been controlled by many social and political factors and sometimes the church gave way to the interests of the emperors, and thereby lost its identity."¹The European feudal system also laid a solid foundation for priestly domination. ² During the Reformation, the western Church kept the laity out of everything; even active involvement of the lay in liturgical

worship was disregarded. On the other hand, in the Eastern Church, an administrative system has emerged with the participation of the laity. Their rights were duly recognized in church administration, liturgy and doctrinal matters. They have an ecclesial tradition in which the bishops gave spiritual leadership while the stewardship of temporal affairs was looked after by the committees, which included the laypeople.

2. Participation of People of God in the Malankara Church Before 16th century

From the very early period itself, the Malankara church followed a kind of synodal structure by actively engaging its laity in the day to day affairs of the Church. Due representation and prominences were given to the laity. For instance, during Chaldean Patriarch Timothy I (789-823),

¹Cherian C.C., *The People of God*, (Kottayam: Divyabodhanam Publications, 1986.), 75.

²Kanjiramukalil, S., *Ecclesial Identity of the Malankara Catholic Church*, (Kottayam: OIRSI and Bethany Publications, 2002), 108.

there is evidence of the Metropolitan's appointment elected by the people in the presence of suffragan bishops.³

Palli Yogams (Church Assemblies): *Palli Yogams* played an essential role in the ecclesial life of St. Thomas Christians. Since Christians were scattered in various places, their spiritual and temporal affairs were dealt with by the local autonomous assemblies called *Palli Yogams*.⁴ This *Yogam* consists of the representatives of the families⁵ and the clergy of a parish. These *yogams* are presided over by ministers⁶ or presbyters who had been elected by the local people and ordained bishops. The notion of the Church as a communion of fellowship was kept intact and alive through the *Yogam*. The members of the assembly enjoyed equality. It helped them to maintain communion and solidarity among the Christians.⁷

Functions of *Palli Yogams*

- The *Yogam* discusses the problems connected with life and activities of the parish.
- Arranging church festivals
- It selects men for ministry and recommends them to the bishop for ordination, otherwise known as *desakuri*, the official approval of the parish community.

- Sending representatives for the national church assemblies

- The assembly exercised excommunicating public delinquents, and they had to undergo the punishment imposed by the assembly.
- It functions as a court of justice and settles quarrels and moral lapses

Pothu Yogams: The delegates of all the churches handled Matters that concerned the whole Church. This sort of assembly is known as *pothu yogam* or general assemblies. The general assembly was presided over by Archdeacon.⁸ He is otherwise known as *Jathikkukarthavyan* (leader of the people).

3. Concept of Synodality in the life of Mar Ivanios

Mar Ivanios had the vision of 'walking together' in the ecclesiastical affair from his early days. For instance, we see the concept of synodality in the II Bethany Yogam speech of Mar Ivanios. When he is about to reunite with the Catholic Church, he gathered all the well-wishers and contributors of Bethany and said he would be leaving Bethany soon. So he entrusted them to decide on the

³Koodapuzha, X., "The Ecclesiology of the Thomas Chistians of India," in Vellilamthadam, T., (ed.)*Ecclesial Identity of the Thomas Christians*, (Kottayam: OIRSI, 1985), 73.

⁴*PalliYogams* seems to be originated based on the ancient village assembly which was prevalent among Dravidians. The Dravidians of *sanghakalam*(1-5 cen. AD) used to gather together to discuss matters of common interest and take decisions on them. This assembly was an authoritative body at the village level. The families are obliged to abide by the decisions of the assembly. In the same way *palliyogams* was responsible for the welfare of the Christian community and it seems to be influenced also by the Jewish synagogue organization pattern.

⁵ In the early phase the head of each caste or class were allowed to attend the assemblies. Later, the head of each family was given the chance, including women. But in the course of time all adult men of the family were allowed and participation of women was discarded.

⁶Each assembly had at least one minister as its president. He was known as '*cassanari*' or '*kathanar*' which means a man of *karthan*(Lord). Cherian C.C., *The People of God*,81.

⁷Koodapuzha, X., "The Ecclesiology of the Thomas Chistians of India," in Vellilamthadam, T., (ed.)*Ecclesial Identity of the Thomas Christians*, 79.

⁸ Podipara, P., *The Hierarchy of the Syro-Malabar Church*, (Alleppey: Prakasam Publication, 1976.), 106.

temporal goods of Bethany. He says, “Whatever you decide, I am ready to act on your decision in this matter. Even if the property is acquired in my name, I am willing to write a contract or other document

to someone of your choice.”⁹ The inclusive attitude of Mar Ivanios is seen here. Being a bishop and the sole authority of Bethany, he could have decided on his discretion. But he never does so. Instead, he gathered and listened to the opinion of the others. He wished the participation of all in the execution of Bethany.

Upadesi System: The vision of the participation of lay catechists in the Catholic Church was envisaged in the second Vatican council. It teaches, “In our time when there are so few clerics to preach the Gospel to such great numbers and to exercise the pastoral ministry, the position of catechists is of great importance.” But a few decades before this teaching and vision of Vatican II was implemented in the mission fields of Malankara Catholic Church by instituting the system of *upadesis*. So he initiated many educated lay faithful, including women, into missionary activities in view of the evangelization of India.

Synodality in Syro Malankara Catholic Church: The mission of the Church is one, and all the members of the Church are equally obliged to accomplish that mission. Malankara Catholic Church, by its very nature, has a synodal character. From parish level to eparchial level, Malankara church enjoys the participation of bishops, priests, religious and laity in the daily affairs of the Church.

This participation is accomplished through different organizations which are meant for the laities and the pastors. Therefore, Pastors and laity are responsible for accomplishing the one mission concerning the Church herself and with respect to the world.

Synodality in Parish Level: Parish committee (*itavaka committee*): The particular code of Syro Malankara Catholic Church (CPCSMCC) defines the parish committee as the representative body elected by the parish general Body¹⁰ (*itavaka pothuyogam*). A parish committee is through which a representative body of the people of God in the parish, in communion with one another and with their parish priest, meets to deliberate and resolve in common agreements on spiritual, pastoral, and temporal matters according to the norms of a particular law and eparchial statutes.

The parish committee must have members from the entire portion of the people of God, namely clerics, religious, and laity. The legislation is an expression of the conciliar theology. The committee is to reflect the participation of people from diverse states of life to ensure their specific way of serving the mission of the entire parish. According to CPCSMCC, representatives from the MCYM, the MCA, *Pithrvedi*, *Matrvedi*, Catechism Teachers, Prayer Groups are also members of *itavaka committee*.¹¹ It shows the wide range of participation of the people of God from different strata of life. The parish committee is a body to inspire a spirit of loving communion between the parish priest and the parishioners and not a body to provoke a spirit of confrontation. Therefore, there should not be a domineering spirit on either side. Priests have to

⁹ Thomas Mar Anthonios, “Bethany YogamPrasangam” in *Vishwasadhorani*, (Trivandrum: Catholicate Centre, 2010), 129-130.

¹⁰CPCSMCC, can. 159.

¹¹CPCSMCC, can. 162.

acknowledge the rights and duties of the laity, and the laypeople should offer their pastors a sincere and selfless collaboration in a spirit of filial respect and real concern for the building up of the community.

The parish priest has the power to convene the council and to take the decision at the end of the consultation. On the other hand, unfortunately, some parish priests, especially those unaware of the genuine meaning of shared responsibility and the whole progress of the consultative process in the post-conciliar Church, tend not to share the power in the process of decision making. As a result, an atmosphere of mistrust and rivalry is created that seriously affects the entire parish's goodwill and growth.

The main functions of the parish committee can be summed up as:

- To co-ordinate and animate the entire Christian life of the community in co-responsibility with the pastor and keeping in mind the priorities of the eparchy.
- To foster a growing sense of community in the parish
- To identify the various needs of the parish and to draw up and carry out suitable plans for the overall growth of the parish as a community of faith, love and witness.
- To foster collaboration among all the parishioners and parish associations in the building up of the parish.
- To animate and co-ordinate the activities of the various groups of association in the parish with a view of promoting healthy interaction among them

4. Different Kinds of Association in SMCC

There are certain associations in the Syro Malankara Catholic Church that are meant to promote the Christian vocation in the world and engage in charitable and pious activities.¹² Each association of Christian faithful of Syro Malankara Catholic Church is erected by a competent ecclesiastical authority as a Juridic person. The Malankara Catholic Children's League (MCCL), the Malankara Catholic Youth Movement (MCYM), the Malankara Catholic Association (MCA), the Malankara catholic *Pitruvedi*(MCP) and the Malankara catholic *Matruvei* (MCM) are recognized as association proper to Malankara Catholic Church.¹³

By the law itself, all the catechism children in the Syro Malankara Catholic Church are members of MCCL. Through MCCL and Sunday school programs, children are equipped and formed in Christian life. The early catechetical formation makes a substantial effect on one's own life. Their voices should be listened to by the ecclesial authorities and the parents.

The Malankara catholic youth movement is not merely a social forum; rather, it constitutes the very young Malankara Catholic Church who tries to fulfil its mission in the given situation. MCYM cultivates an interest in church worship and practices and enables one to lead an exemplary sacramental life. It empowers the youth to respond boldly against social evils and to work for the building of a new society through creative action based on Christian teachings.¹⁴ Being the sprouting buds, they should be actively made participate in the mission of the Church, and their opinions should be sought. But now, there is a

¹²CPCSMCC, can. 393.

¹³CPCSMCC, can. 406.

¹⁴ *Bharanakatana*, MCYM., (Major Archdiocese Trivandrum, 2004) 9.

tendency in the Church to set apart and considering the youth as immature and unsophisticated, especially in the process of decision making. Such kind of tendencies is against the essence of synodality.

MCA, MCP, MCM are other forums of the Syro Malankara catholic church for the faithful who are above the age of 35 years. These associations are constituted with a clear and definitive ecclesial vision for promoting the Malankara Catholic Church in its various apostolates. The catechesis given to these groups by various means such as seminars, meetings, gospel conventions, family prayer meetings and liturgical prayer meetings are examples of their active participation in the Church.

DIOCESAN LEVEL

Pastoral Councils: Pastoral council in the diocesan level is constituted to assist and promote all that relates to the pastoral work of the eparchy and to offer practical suggestions so that the life and activities so the life of the faithful may be brought in conformity with the mind of the Church. Thirty-five percent of the total number of pastoral council members shall be women.¹⁵ But particular law does not stipulate how the election of the laity into the diocesan pastoral councils should be conducted.

Presbyteral Council and Eparchial Consulters: the Presbyteral council is a body of the priests representing the presbyterate of the eparchy, which assists the eparchial bishop by its advice in those things that regard to the pastoral and other common good of the eparchy.¹⁶ Eparchial consulters are appointed by the eparchial bishop, which helps the bishop in administration.

¹⁵CPCSMCC, can. 114.

¹⁶CCEO can. 264.

District Level: Each ecclesiastical district of SMCC has a pastoral council which consists of parish priests, superiors of religious houses, members of eparchial pastoral councils from the eccl. District, trustee (*kaikaran*) and secretary from each parish, a lay woman participant from each parish, elected lay faithful who are conferred with eccl. Titles and one representative from each association and apostolate from the ecclesiastical district. The council's functions are¹⁷:

- To cooperate in the building up of the Church
- To co-ordinate the apostolic activities and ecclesiastical discipline
- Implementing the instructions given in the pastoral letters
- To Discuss and propose a solution to the religious problems
- To Study the urgent need and suggests prudent ways of handling them
- To evaluate and offer timely solutions to ecclesiastical challenges

5. OTHER SYSTEMS WHICH INCLUDE LAY PARTICIPATION

SMCC ensures various other provisions also for laities in the administrative section. Each eparchy can have eparchial commissions and departments for various apostolates. They are under the guidance of the eparchial bishop. Lay faithful or religious can be appointed as secretary to the priest who is the director of a commission.¹⁸

In Finance Council: finance council is constituted with two lay Christians from the pastoral council, two presbyteral

¹⁷CPCSMCC, cans. 120,121,122.

¹⁸CPCSMCC, can. 111.

council members and three other members other than the finance officer, freely appointed by the eparchial bishop.¹⁹

In liturgy: recently, the provision for reading the epistle amidst the Holy Qurbano is granted for the woman faithful, which was reserved only to the men earlier.

Syro Malankara Catholic Assembly: to ensure the diverse participation of people of God in the mission and life of the church, SMCC constitutes an assembly following the norm of CCEO. It discusses various topics and collects suggestions from each parish, and tries to put them into practice if it is necessary.

Suvishesha Sangam: through baptism, each faithful participates in the mission of the Church. Each person is obliged and possesses the right to proclaim the gospel message. *Suvishesha Sangam* is a movement in SMCC which enhance the spiritual awakening of the Church by the active participation of the laity. By using their different charisms, evangelization in the Church is being done. They visit the houses and conduct prayers, and more than that, they live the Gospel values and witness Christ before the world.

Laity in SMCC missions: The role and contributions of the laity in the mission places of our Church are highly notable and appreciable. The pastors could access the places where priests and religious cannot reach. Those who are working in the mission of SMCC are independent pastors. They are given our catechetical courses. They guide the communities according to our church teachings with the help of our priests and sisters.

Safe Environment Committee: As per the new civil law, there should be a safe environment committee in each

diocese under the presidency of the eparchial bishop in collaboration with the civil system. It says that the presbyteries, Churches, educational institutions, religious institutions, houses of special care, and Catholic organizations should be places where all feel comfortable. The primary purposes of this committee are;

- Provide a secure and safe environment for minors and vulnerable adults in the faith communities within our dioceses/eparchies.
- Emphasize the need for reporting any incident of sexual assault or harassment to the Church authorities as well as to the civil authorities;
- Address the spiritual, physical, and emotional causes of the victims, their families, and the affected community
- Address the possibility of false accusations against clergy, employees, and volunteers.

The Major Archi-eparchial Synod of the Syro-Malankara Catholic Church also provides much importance and attention to the safe environment committee. Among its five members, three seats are reserved for the laity. It is based on the basic Christian values and morals issued by the CBCI and the provisions of the Protection of Children from Sexual Offences (POCSO) Act, 2012, of India.

6. Conclusion

Concerning lay participation, the Syro Malankara Catholic Church is practicing a blend of the traditional approach of St. Thomas Christians and the western approach of synodality. The present parish councils and pastoral councils have a democratic setup but we need to think that in practicality how much it enjoys full administrative freedom. Are they merely advisory bodies?

¹⁹CPCSMCC, can. 106.

The lay participation that the ancient Syrian Christians enjoyed and practiced is not reflected in the present system. The ancient privileges and authority of the laity to give approval of the candidates to priesthood and elevation of bishop²⁰ etc... are denied in the present administrative system. Laity should be incorporated, and due representation has to be given to them in the practical fields such as evangelization, economic affairs and social development activities.

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Thomas Mar Anthonios, "Bethany YogamPrsangam" in *Vishwasadhorani*, (Trivandrum: Catholicate Centre, 2010), 129-130.

²⁰We often witness elections that are politicized among other Christian denominations. Campaigning is dangerous. In the early days of the Catholic Church, the apostles and their successors elected and consecrated bishops by getting consensus among the people. Obviously people were not choosing, they were generally expressing their consent technically called as 'oxios' which means

worthy. (Thomas Mar Koorilos, "Sabhaniyamangal," (ed.) Kakkannattu A. *Atmabodhanam* (Trivandrum: Suvishesha Sangam, 2020), 779.

AN INTRODUCTION TO THE TRANSCENDENTAL LEAP

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Abstract: This paper is an attempt to introduce and explain the term Transcendental Leap in the field of semantics. With this concept, the process of meaning-making is explained more clearly. The semantic process of Transcendental Leap takes place within the Neuro-context of a person. Therefore, the transcendental leap varies in accordance with the expansion of one's neuro-context. This academic paper opens the door of linguistics to the field of science, especially to Neuro-Linguistics. The academic paper does not deal with anything with regard to the brain and its physiology directly, whereas it is directed towards the same. This concept is explained with the imagery of 'the Medicine of Life' of St Ephrem which is used to denote the Holy Eucharist.

Key Words: Transcendental Leap, Neuro-Context, Linguistics, Hermeneutics, Theory of Interpretation

1. INTRODUCTION

The proposed academic paper, "An Introduction to Transcendental Leap" is an attempt to study the pattern of meaning generation with special reference to Ephrem's way of theologization by making use of the Eucharistic imagery of *the Medicine of Life*. The main purpose of this study is to analyze the shift of meaning in the Eucharistic imagery of *the Medicine of Life*. Why is it significant? This analysis will enable a person to understand an imagery or any form of expression in language. This academic paper not only studies the 'what' aspect of semantics but also the 'how' and 'why' dimensions too. To give a better clarification of these aspects to the postmodern world, few new terms are introduced in this academic paper to explain the process of meaning generation. Those terms are 'transcendental leap', 'neuro context (NC)', 'fragmentary neuro context', and 'collective neuro context'. The semantic shift of the Eucharistic imagery of *the Medicine of Life* is analyzed with the said technical terms.

2. TRANSCENDENTAL LEAP

All these linguistic terms represent the formation of an idea and its shift of meaning. The semantic shift is indicated with the term transcendental leap (TL). Transcendental Leap cannot be understood as a synonym with a semantic shift in

linguistics (suggestiveness). Whereas it goes beyond the physical world to the metaphysical world when it comes in the religious and theological language. Therefore, TL is the process of interpret the divine revelation in the human language. For example, the meaning of the phrase 'New Jerusalem' is not 'a modern Jerusalem' when TL takes place. The said phrase will get an eschatological interpretation. What will be the situation if this eschatological dimension of the meaning is not transferred to the reader? When we deal with the religious language and theological language TL is a necessary linguistic phenomenon. Therefore, in TL both the process of meaning generation and the semantic leap are included. In normal cases, semantic change is the result of cognition. Whereas in TL it is the result of cognition, contemplation and divine revelation. Where does and how does this complex process take place? The direct answer to this question is in the brain with the neural network which is exposed to sensory experiences and divine revelation. In this academic paper we do not intend to enter directly into any physiological explanations, but I will be using the terms such as Neuro Context (NC), Fragmentary Neuro Context (FNC,) and Collective Neuro Context (CNC). Since these terms are new inventions to explain the Theo-semantic phenomenon of Transcendental Leap (TL), a short introduction is given to

the use of these terms (see Figure 1). The term *Neuro Context* stands for the entire sensory information and the capacity to cobble new ideas by making use of the existing information. It means that *Neuro Context* is always dynamic and open-ended. Therefore, *Neuro Context* can be defined as the total of the received data the neural ability to manipulate data to generate new knowledge, and the ability to go beyond the data at the same time to contact the new context.¹

Neuro Context is always connected to *Collective Neuro Context (CNC)* as it is portrayed in *Figure 1*. Since it is dynamic in its very nature it is always widening until it ceases to exist. When a person hears, sees, touches, tastes or smells something the data become part of the *Neuro Context*. The reason for combining the words ‘neuro’ and ‘context’ is to indicate the neural activity and the space where it takes place. Therefore, the words ‘neuro’ and ‘context’ in the term *Neuro Contexts* and for the continuous neural networking and the brain. Since we are not dealing directly with neurolinguistics here in this thesis, we will be focusing on the ideological aspect of *Neuro Context*. Why *Neuro Context* becomes significant is that it will help a person how to read religious and theological works. *Neuro Contextual Analysis*

Figure 1: Transcendental Leap

enables a person to understand how a theologian thought. This analysis helps the process of theologization. Now I will explain the how *Neuro Contextual Analysis* functions. As you see in *Figure 1* there are many factors included in CNC such as Divine Revelation, Nature, Culture, People,

Available Knowledge and so on. Therefore, *Neuro-context* is the result of continuous communication. Slowly *Neuro*

Context produces *Fragmentary Neuro Context (FNC)*. Any expression or literary work comes under *Fragmentary Neuro Context*. That means within a lifetime a person creates millions of *Fragmentary Neuro Contexts*. The preserved *Fragmentary Neuro Contexts* are used for references (Like a book of an author). It means that each *Fragmentary Neuro Context* points to the source from which it originated (ie.NC). No one gets a direct entry to anyone’s *Neuro Context* without the help of an available *Fragmentary Neuro Context*. Therefore, the proper understanding of any *Fragmentary Neuro Context* primarily demands research in the CNC and other *Fragmentary Neuro Contexts* of the NC of the author.

If the author is NC¹, then the reader is NC² as it is portrayed in *Figure 1*. When the reader starts exploring NC¹ occurs at least four types of dialogue as it is indicated in the picture with arrows.

- NC² – FNC¹ — NC² — FNC² (TL¹ and TL² will be similar or advanced)
- NC² – CNC¹ — FNC¹ — FNC² (TL¹ and TL² will be similar or advanced)
- NC² – FNC¹ — CNC¹ — FNC² (TL¹ and TL² will be similar or advanced)
- NC² – FNC¹ — FNC² (TL¹ and TL² are not be similar, but advanced)

In the case of religious language and theological language a special linguistic phenomenon takes place and that is called *Transcendental Leap (TL)*. It means that each religious or theological work generates a shift in meaning in the minds of the reader. That means when this shift happens the *signifier* transcends its limits brings the minds of the reader to the *signified* which is metaphysical or divine. It is the result of *Transcendental Leap* in the NC²(reader). If the reader is not accustomed with the CNC¹ and FNC¹ the desired leap will not take place, but there will be a kind of *Transcendental Leap* as in the case of ‘d’. The *Transcendental Leap* always directed to God and the

¹ Cf. J.John, “Neuro Contextual Analysis of Sacramental Symbols” *Ensygloge: An International Journal for Arts and Science* (January-June, 2021, Published on 1st June 2021, Vol 1,

Issue 1),p.2 [<https://www.ensyglodge.com>](accessed October, 2021)

economy of salvation. *Neuro contextual analysis* studies how this transcendental leap occurs.

So if a person is 20 years of age that person's *Neuro Context* consists of 20 years' entire experiences and the continuous generation of ideas by making use of the past and present experiences. It means a person's *Neuro Context* is always infused with the society and the culture to which he-she e is part. That means the person's *Neuro Context* is always in communication with the existing *Neuro Contexts* (CNC). This connected network of existing *Neuro Contexts* is known as *Collective Neuro Context* (CNC). It means a person is born into the matrix of CNC. Therefore, it is necessary to know the particular CNC to which a new *Neuro Context* is used in order to trace out the exact meaning of all the meaning of the *Fragmentary Neuro Contexts* (FNC). The term *Fragmentary Neuro Contexts* refers to all the stored or preserved data or information outside a person in any form available to others. It is part of the CNC, because NC is always in dialogue with CNC. For example, if I write a book, make a phrase or a statement, draw a picture or make a gesture it becomes a *Fragmentary Neuro Context*. It means that *Fragmentary Neuro Context* itself is emanate either from *Neuro Context* or from the *Collective Neuro Context* is the visible. It is the connecting link to NC and CNC. It has the capability of a causing *Transcendental Leap*. For example, the Eucharistic of imagery *the Medicine of Life* is a fragmentary neuro context. To find out the *Transcendental Leap* of this FNC, it is necessary to study how the NC of the author of the said imagery is developed and to which CNC the author and the reader were exposed. It also means that there are many CNCs influences a particular NC. Therefore, every FNC is the outcome of the ameliorated version from the NC. This is an open ended process. It means that this process never stops. It means even that such a small phrase will generate different levels of meaning and culminates it in the *Transcendental Leap*. I will discuss this in the succeeding chapters.

Since this study takes place in the 21st century it is not possible to get a direct entry to the CNC and NC of St

Ephrem, but it is possible to reason the treasures out of the available resources such as the works of St Ephrem,

Secondary Sources about him and about his works and so on. As it was stated all these are the available *Fragmentary Neuro Contexts* which directs to the *Neuro Context* and *Collective Neuro Context* of St Ephrem. Otherwise we will directly associate and interpret the FNC of St Ephrem within our own NCs which are not exposed to the CNC and NC of St Ephrem and finally and with entirely different interpretation which St Ephrem had not thought of. Therefore, in this thesis I am trying to analyze how the Eucharistic imagery *the Medicine of Life* has got the *Transcendental Leap* and try to find out the theological meaning encapsulated with the said imagery with the help of *Neuro Contextual Analysis*.

Here I am following the second pattern of dialogue (NC² — CNC¹ — FNC¹ — FNC² [TL¹ and TL² will be similar or advanced]).

Therefore, as it is depicted in *Figure 1*, it is necessary to understand the cultural background of St Ephrem (CNC¹ to get a wider look at the formation of the theological formation of St Ephrem. It is this understanding gives clarity with regard to the *Transcendental Leap* of the Eucharistic Imagery *the Medicine of Life*. According to Sebastian Brock, there are nearly 500 hymns of St Ephrem are available and all these hymns are product of a life of profound and meditative reading of the Scriptures.² According to H.E. Mar Joseph Kallarangattu, the oriental liturgical theology is based on the dictum *Lex Orandi Lex Credendi*.³ It means law of the prayer is the law of faith. That means the theology in the Church is interpreted within the liturgy of the Church. Apart from this background study, the biblical, patristic and liturgical realms also will be given due importance. The main formative influences identified and discussed here are the ancient Mesopotamian, Jewish and Greek.⁴ The analysis of the historical background of St Ephrem gives clarity with regard to his theologization. The analytical study of the *Transcendental Leap* of the Eucharistic Imagery *the Medicine of Life* is further

² Cf. S. Brock, "A Hymn of St Ephrem on the Eucharist" in *The Harp*, (1987,1988) Vol 1, Issue 1-3, 63.

³ Cf. J. Kallarangattu, *Kizhakkinte Daivasastra Aadhyathmika Parambaryangal* (Kottayam: OIRSI, 1999), 18.

⁴ Cf. S. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature* (Kottayam: SEERI, 1997) 9.

developed based on this analysis. The different dimensions of the Eucharistic imagery is primarily based on the historical background.

3. CONCLUSION

The imagery the *Medicine of Life* is one of the key imageries in the work of St Ephrem. This imagery is the key by which St Ephrem unlocked the mystery of salvation through the Eucharistic theology. Therefore, a detailed search in the work of St Ephrem is required to find out how and what sense the imagery the medicine of life is used. According to Aron C.T. Smith, "Cultural explanations for religion focus on practices and behaviours while cognitive and evolutionary explanations rely on the assumption that faith comes naturally. At the same time, the neuroscientific evidence suggests that religious thought engages the same brain structures as any strong beliefs, distributed through both emotional rational centers."⁵ It means that religious cognition and theologization cannot be considered as unique form of cognition, for both these are rooted in the ordinary representations.⁶ This argument cannot be true completely. Though all religious experiences are entrenched in the same structure where all other strong believes are centered stimulation that makes the ordinary to extraordinary is different.

In the said case a kind of transcendental leap of meaning takes place. Modern cognitive science considers it as a kind of paradigmatic grafting where cognitive science builds new explanations by cobbling together old ones from multiple disciplines.⁷ But in the case of transcendental analysis mere cobbling of ideas may not lead to the Transcend the leap. Here one requires the faith in God. The revealed mystery of salvation is received gradually by submitting oneself humbly before God. When one humbles oneself before God the divine mysteries will be revealed to him. The revealed mysteries will be understood and expressed with the available information in the neuro context. It means transcendental league is the process of understanding the divine mysteries with the eye of faith by making of the

fragmentary neuro context within the neuro context. Therefore, in the General Conclusion, I will analyze the transcendental leap of the said Eucharistic imageries in order to explain how this leap happens in St Ephrem's literature.

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⁶ Cf. Aaron C.T., *Thinking about Religion: Extending the Cognitive Science of Religion*, 33.

⁷ Cf. Aaron C.T., *Thinking about Religion: Extending the Cognitive Science of Religion*, 76.

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AN INTRODUCTION TO ST. EPHREM

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Abstract: This academic paper is an attempt to analyze the cultural background of St. Ephrem. This paper provides a broader look at the theological formation of St. Ephrem. The cultural influence is very vital in understanding the works of St Ephrem. Major Ephremian Eucharistic imageries are also introduced here briefly.

Key Words: St Ephrem, Medicine of Life, Eucharistic Imagery

1. INTRODUCTION

Every human being is fashioned within the culture of which he or she is part. Therefore, the study of the works of St. Ephrem must begin with a historical search to the Life of St. Ephrem to unleash the theological treasures of his works. Ephrem the Syrian (306-373), born in Nisibis and served as a deacon in Edessa, is a prominent Christian theologian poet.¹ All Churches with apostolic traditions venerate him as a saint. He has written multifarious hymns, poems, sermons, and prose exegesis. According to P. S. Russel, "Ephrem displays delicacy of touch in his use of scripture."² He used many composite images in his works.³ Sebastian Brock brings a beautiful comparison of the imageries used by St. Ephrem, such as 'the Robe of Glory' and 'the Medicine of Life,' which indicate the sacraments of 'Baptism' and 'Holy Eucharist' respectively. He says that a person is gifted the Robe of Glory in Baptism and granted The Medicine of Life in the Holy Eucharist.⁴ He quotes St. Ephrem, "Our Lord baptized humankind with the Holy

Spirit, he nourished it with The Medicine of Life (Nisibian Hymns 46:8)."⁵ The works of St. Ephrem were the need of the time because he lived in a society where Arians, Marcionites, Manicheans, Bardaisanites, and such gnostic sects propagated heresies.⁶ Therefore, it is true to say that the majority of his works were intended for defending the true faith and teachings of the Church. His reflection of the Divine Mysteries made him popular because the theological depth in his works was very great. That is the reason why even now his theological reflections are used in the liturgy of the Church.

There existed a mixed culture consisting of polytheism, Judaism, and several Christian denominations in Nisibis at the time of St. Ephrem. The linguistic culture was also like the same. The ordinary means of communication was Aramaic. Greek and Latin were used as the administrative language.⁷ Therefore, it is necessary to know the specialties of the complex ethnicities before reading St. Ephrem.

¹ Cf. T. Paniker, "St Ephrem and the Eucharist" in *Aikya Samiksha*, II/1 (2005) 5.

Cf. P. S. Russel, *St Ephrem the Syrian and St Gregory the Theologian Confront the Aryans* (Kottayam: SEERI, 1994) 11.

² P. S. Russel, *St Ephrem the Syrian and St Gregory the Theologian Confront the Aryans*, 41.

³ Cf. P. S. Russel, *St Ephrem the Syrian and St Gregory the Theologian Confront the Aryans*, 86.

⁴ Cf. S. Brock, "A Hymn of St Ephrem on the Eucharist", 63.

⁵ Cf. S. Brock, "A Hymn of St Ephrem on the Eucharist", 64.

⁶ Cf. G. John, *Swargeeyamanna* (Mavelikara: St. Paul's Book Depot, 1989) 187.

⁷ Cf. Aprem, *Mar Aprem, Theologian & Poet* (Kottayam: SEERI, 1990) 9-10. (N.B. Here the author is a bishop from Kerala)

Mar Jacob, a signatory in the First Council of Nicaea (325 CE), was the bishop of Nisibis. Ephrem was doing his ministry under him (later, this ministry gained him the title The Founder of the School of Nisibis). It was Mar Jacob who gave diaconate to St. Ephrem. The sudden upheavals in the political scenario of that time caused a drastic change in the Life of St. Ephrem. The edict of Milan legalized Christianity in the Roman Empire in 313. The death of Emperor Constantine I and the inability of the successors to protect the Empire offered a golden opportunity to Shapur II of Persia to besiege Nisibis in 338 CE. So we come across the second phase of St. Ephrem as a refugee in Edessa. All these political instabilities were well narrated poetically in “The Hymn of Nisibis”. He has compared this political situation with that of the Ark of Noah in the book of Genesis. Shapur again attacked the surrounding cities of Nisibis around 359 CE. Constantius II could not respond, and the campaign of Julian ended by witnessing his sorrowful death in 363. His successor Jovian was forced to surrender Nisibis to Persia, and it culminated with the expulsion of the entire Christian population to Persia.⁸ Therefore, the second phase of the Life of St. Ephrem was spent in the school of Edessa, where Syriac, a dialect of Aramaic, was spoken. As stated above, he was also confronted by Arianism, Marcionism, Manicheism, and several types of Gnostic teachings.⁹ He defended the Nicene orthodoxy through his hymns. According to Aprem:

He [St. Ephrem] preached many sermons against the heretics. His eloquence kept his audience spell-bound and often moved them to tears. As a participant in the Council of Nicea, he defended Nicene Orthodoxy against Arians, Bardaisan, Marcion, and Mani. His poems and sermons are a great authority for theologians of the Church of the East as well as of the

Universal Church. His teachings about the Trinity, the Incarnation, the Eucharist, and Virgin Mary, were strong barriers against contemporary and later heresies.¹⁰

All the works of St. Ephrem are not available, but around four hundred hymns are still preserved. Ephrem is a vantage point of many cultural heritages, such as Judaism, Greek Philosophy, and Mesopotamian tradition of symbols. The majority of his literary works are in lyrical form. All those lyrics are pedagogical hymns.¹¹ The poetic scheme of Bardaisan might have influenced him, and he used the same poetic form (*Madrashé*) to defend the faith by devising the hymns with doctrines to make the Christians conscious about the heretic teaching.¹² Apart from poetry, he used verse homilies (*memre*) and biblical commentaries too.

As stated in the preceding paragraphs, St. Ephrem used the poetic form to teach the catholic doctrines and implemented those hymns in the prayers.¹³ Therefore, the Syriac churches used the works of St. Ephrem in the liturgy and canonical prayers. Moreover, since the zealous missionaries from the Persian Church did mission work in the far East, the St. Thomas Christians are also influenced by the teachings of St. Ephrem.

2. ST. EPHREM AND THE SYRIAC CHRISTIANITY IN THE EAST

Christianity began in Jerusalem. Later it spread to other places in Asia too. Christianity in Nisibis and Edessa is generally known as Syriac Christianity because the celebration of the liturgy and writing of theology was in the Syriac language. Like Greek and Latin, Syriac was also one of the main languages of early Christianity. As said in the introduction, Nisibis was under Roman Empire until the time of the Persian invasion. The Edict of Milan granted religious freedom to Christians, and it was one of the reasons for spreading the Christian faith in the place of the

humanity and divinity represents peace, perfection and salvation; in contrast, docetism and other heresies sought to divide or reduce Christ's nature and, in doing so, rend and devalue Christ's followers with their false teachings.” Cf. P. S. Russel, *St Ephrem the Syrian and St Gregory the Theologian Confront the Aryans*, 7.

¹³ Cf. T. Paniker, “St Ephrem and the Eucharist,” 5.

⁸ Cf. Aprem, *Mar Aprem, Theologian & Poet*, 17.

⁹ Cf. G. John, *Swargeeyamanna*, 187.

¹⁰ Aprem, *Mar Aprem, Theologian & Poet*, 18

¹¹ Aprem, *Mar Aprem, Theologian & Poet*, 18

¹² “The Hymns Against Heresies employ colourful metaphors to describe the Incarnation of Christ as fully human and divine. Ephrem asserts that Christ's unity of

Roman Empire. The heretic influences were hazardous to the Catholic Faith of the Syriac Christians in Nisibis at the time of St. Ephrem. Ephrem had to defend Faith from heresies like Gnosticism, Marcionism, Manicheism, and above all, from Arianism.

3. SYRIAC LITERATURE AT THE TIME OF ST.

EPHREM

Syriac was used as the literary language of Aramaic speaking Christianity in the early centuries.¹⁴ There were many literary works in Syriac from the second to the twentieth century. This long period of Syriac literature can be divided into six periods for the convenience of analyzing the literary works by classifying the ascetic authors and other writers. The periods of Syriac literature are; a) the earliest literature (2 & 3 century), b) the golden age of Syriac literature (4th C), c) fifth to mid-seventh century, d) mid-seventh to the end of the thirteenth century, e) 14th – 19th century, and f) the 20th century. Due to Arab invasion (7-20th C), the writers of the Syriac churches preferred (or were forced) to write Arabic rather than Syriac.¹⁵ Therefore, the Syriac Christian Scholars of the 19th century played a vital role in translating Greek Philosophy and science to the Arab World. In this process, all those literary and philosophical works in Greek were translated first to Syriac and then to Arabic. Later those works were translated to Latin from Arabic. Therefore it is true that Syriac was a bridge in connecting Greek Philosophy to Western Europe.¹⁶

Here our concern of Syriac Literature rests upon the first two periods of the Syriac literature. First, the pre-Ephremic works including *the Diatessaron, the Old Syriac Gospels, Works of Bardaisan, the Odes of Solomon, the Acts of Thomas, the Works attributed to Melito the Philosopher, the Syriac Sentences of Menander, the Letter of Mara, the*

Story of the Armaean Sage Ahikas and so on.¹⁷ Among these early Syriac writings, the first five works are significant when we analyze the poetical works of St. Ephrem. When the literary works of St. Ephrem are analyzed, it is very evident that he was influenced by the writing style (writing in meter) of Bardaisan and the allusive character of the *Odes of Solomon*.¹⁸

In the first two centuries, Baptismal and the Eucharistic theologies were very strong. The early Syriac Christianity was acquainted with symbols and imageries. Therefore, we find allusive language in the Syriac literature. The religious persecution and the life situation might have been the two prominent reasons for using this kind of allusive language in literature. This is what we see in the *Odes of Solomon*. In the same way, Bardaisan of Edessa also used allusive language to spread wrong teachings. He tried to interpret Christology by using the existing astrology and metaphysics and ended in heresy.¹⁹ Even then, he contributed a poetic style to Syriac Literature (pentameter). He taught that the incarnation of Jesus Christ was to restore the harmony of cosmic elements (fire, water, earth, and air). Apart from the heretic teachings of Bardaisan, Aryanism was also prevalent in society.

Another prominent theologian in Syriac literature was Aphrahat (+145). His theology was based on Judaism. He lived in the interior parts of the Persian Empire. He contributed 23 demonstrations in Syriac. These are some of the pre-Ephremian works in the Syriac literature. When these works are scrutinized, it is very clear that there is a gradual growth in the development of theology as well as poetical style.

¹⁴ Cf. S. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature in Moran Etho-9* (Kottayam: SEERI, 1997) 7.

¹⁵ “Period D (7th -13th cent.) belongs to the time of the Omayyads (7th – 8th century), ‘Abbasids (750c.- 1100), Seljuks (in Turkey, 11th/12th centuries) and Mongols (from 13th century). Period E (14th -19th cent.) belongs to the time of (successively) Mongol, Mamluk (along with other local dynasties), and Ottoman rule in Western Asia, and opened with a time of great devastation and destruction through war

and the Black Death. Period F (20th cent.) belongs to the time of the breakup of the Ottoman Empire and the emergence of the modern nation states in West Asia.” Cf. S. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac*, 10.

¹⁶ Cf. S. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature*, 11.

¹⁷ Cf. S. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature*, 14-18.

¹⁸ Cf. S. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature*, 14-28.

¹⁹ Cf. S. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature*, 15.

3.1. CULTURAL BACKGROUND

St. Ephrem is a culmination of three cultures such as Greek, Jewish, and Mesopotamian traditions.²⁰ This triple heritage is visible in his writings. According to Aprem, “Mar Aprem introduced acrostics into Syriac poetry, in imitation of some Hebrew poems, each strophe of which began with a letter of the alphabet.”²¹ The Eucharistic metaphor of the Medicine of Life is one of the prominent examples of the ancient Mesopotamian cultural influence.²² This imagery refers to Jesus Christ and the Eucharist in all the works of St. Ephrem. Many of the imageries were taken from the Old Testament (*The Hymn on Paradise* is one of the best examples.), and it shows that he used to refer Jewish Bible. Ephrem was also influenced by Greek culture. For example, the Greek concept of purification is visible in his works. He was aware of the way of the theological thinking of the Greek Christians. These three cultural heritages are fine-tuned in the writings of St. Ephrem.

3.2. ST. EPHREM’S INFLUENCE AND CONTRIBUTION TO SYRIAC LITERATURE

St. Ephrem’s influence on Syriac Literature is remarkable. According to Brock, “St. Ephrem has left a large body of religious poetry, some of it of very great beauty and as a result of his enormous reputation in antiquity, many of his poems were translated into Greek, and so came into influence the great Byzantine liturgical poets, from Romanos onwards.”²³ He was a theologian who

employed poetry as an expressive means to defend the faith.²⁴ He composed poetry in the form of ‘*Memre*’ and ‘*Madrasha*’.²⁵ He introduced the twelve syllabled (doceca syllabic) metre into Syriac poetry.²⁶ His approach to theology is rooted in Scripture, and the method he used for teaching theology was well accepted among the people of God. Ephrem uses many biblical images and symbols in his poems, from describing the Eucharistic Mysteries and the Economy of Salvation.²⁷ The fundamental doctrines of the Catholic Church were easily imprinted in the hearts of the people through his poetic style of heptasyllabic couplets. He made use of the imageries familiar to the people. Therefore, they could associate the content of theology with that of the existing meaning of the imagery and thereby learn the exact meaning of the doctrine. For Example, St. Ephrem explains the incarnation of the Second Person in the Holy Trinity and connects it with the imagery of The Medicine of Life in *Hymn on Nativity* as follows:

Let Eve today rejoice in Sheol,
For her daughter’s Son
has come down as the Medicine of
Life
to revive His mother’s mother
(Nativity 13:2).²⁸

His commentary on the *Diatessaron* deals with the interpretation of the *Diatessaron*. His other contributions to the Syriac literature are *Commentary on Acts*, *Commentary on the Pauline Epistles*, *Prose Refutations* (which includes five discourses addressed to Hypatius, against false doctrine, against Bardaisan, against Marcion, against Mani), *Discourse on Our Lord*, *Letters to Publius* (Eschatological teachings), *Memre on Faith*, *Memre against Bardaisan*, *On*

as the metre of St Ephrem), while the *madrasha* is used for lyric poetry written in stanzas, which can be in a variety of different syllabic metres, though for anyone poem the same meter is adhered to throughout.” S. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature*, 23.

²⁶ Aprem, *Mar Aprem, Theologian & Poet*, 18.

²⁷ Cf. T. Paniker, “St Ephrem and the Eucharist,” 5.

²⁸ Cf. S. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 99.

²⁰ Cf. T. Paniker, “St Ephrem and the Eucharist,” 5.

²¹ Aprem, *Mar Aprem, Theologian & Poet*, 19.

²² Cf. S. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem* (Michigan: Cistercian Publications, 1992) 19-24.

²³ S. Brock, *Studies in Syriac Spirituality*, 53.

²⁴ Cf. S. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 160.

²⁵ “The *memra* is employed for narrative poetry, and is written in couplets consisting of 7+7 syllables (later known

*Jonah and the Repentance of Nineveh, On the Sinful Woman, On Solitudes, Madrashe on Faith, Madrashe on Nisibis,*²⁹ *Madrashe against Heresies* (Marcionism, Bardaisan, Mani, etc.), *Madrashe on Virginity, Madrashe on the Church, Madrashe on Nativity, Madrashe on Unleavened Bread, Madrashe on Paradise, Madrashe on the Fast, Madrashe against Julian* and so on.³⁰

Therefore, his writings remain always new and relevant to the postmodern world. There is no wonder in calling him the “Harp of the Holy Spirit” because the Holy Spirit inspires the saintly people to ruminate over the Scripture and seek the hidden treasures inside. St. Ephrem became influential in the East and the West through his hymns, biblical interpretations, and theological discourses. When his literary works are analyzed, it becomes evident that he developed the Syriac literary style.

4. EUCHARISTIC IMAGES AND SYMBOLS IN ST. EPHREM³¹

The theology of St. Ephrem is known as the theology of imageries and symbols. Symbols go beyond the usual way of thinking. It carries the reality which it symbolizes. Ephrem was aware of the fact that symbols are part of human beings. Therefore, man can reach mystic experience through symbols. Symbols elevate one’s mind from physical to metaphysical reality. Since every symbol has a hidden nature, it must be appropriately interpreted. Here some of the Eucharistic symbols in St. Ephrem’s literary works are analyzed. We will introduce some of the imagery here to avoid repeating those Eucharistic imageries in the second academic paper. Moreover, it will help us to focus on the Eucharistic imagery of the Medicine of Life. Therefore, we will not expound the said imagery in detail here, but we will briefly introduce the same.

The content of the title, “Eucharistic Images and Symbols in St. Ephrem,” is prepared mainly from the findings from the book *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem* by Sebastian Brock. Brock has brilliantly picked out the Eucharistic imageries from the entire hymns of St. Ephrem. It is necessary to get a glimpse over those Eucharistic Imageries. He has pointed out three primary Eucharistic metaphors in *The Luminous Eye*, such as “The Medicine of Life³²,” “The Coal of Fire³³,” and “The Pearl³⁴.” These three imageries will be discussed here in detail to develop the succeeding academic papers. These three imageries are used in the works of St. Ephrem to denote the Holy Eucharist. These Eucharistic imageries show the different aspects of the Eucharist. Ephrem offers a whole profusion of types and symbols to explain the holy Eucharist because symbols are needed for the human intellect to comprehend metaphysical ideas.

4.1. THE MEDICINE OF LIFE

Medicine of Life is the key imagery studied in this dissertation. The analysis and the interpretation of this imagery will probe the fact that religious language can transcend people’s minds to the divine. By using this imagery St. Ephrem proves that Jesus Christ is the Medicine of Life. St. Ephrem has come to this conclusion as a result of his deep meditation of the Holy Scripture and the teachings of the Church. He has been influenced a lot by the Gospel of John. We will explain it in the second academic paper. Apart from this, he uses many Old Testament incidents to define the meaning of this Eucharistic imagery. For example, “Moses hid the symbol of Christ as a Medicine of Life in the unleavened bread.”³⁵ He gradually develops the idea of the Medicine of Life by selectively taking the Old Testament episodes.

²⁹ “These poems deal largely with the history of Nisibis and its bishop and of the adjacent cities...” Cf. Aprem, *Mar Aprem, Theologian & Poet*, 21.

³⁰ Cf. S. Brock, *A Brief Outline of Syriac Literature*, 23-28.

³¹ Cf. S. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 99-114.

³² Cf. S. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 99.

³³ Cf. S. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 103.

³⁴ Cf. S. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 106.

³⁵ G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal* (Kottayam: OIRSI, 2009) 38.

4.2. THE COAL OF FIRE

Ephrem employs the metaphor ‘the coal of fire’ to represent the Eucharist. This imagery is taken from the prophets (Isaiah 6:6). Ephrem says that all the Christians hold and consume Christ, the new Coal of Fire. The same imagery is used in the Holy *Qurbano* of the Syro-Malankara Catholic Church. When the Holy Eucharist is distributed, the priest prays, “The Coal of Fire, which is Your Body and Blood, is given to the true faithful.” It shows how Ephrem’s theology influenced the Catholic Church later.³⁶

4.3. THE PEARL

Ephrem’s poems on the pearl are also an indirect indication of the Eucharist.³⁷ He says in a poem that he took a pearl into his hands and in that he watched the symbols which revealed the images of the Kingdom and the glory of God. That pearl became a fountain from which he drank the mysteries of the Son.³⁸ Ephrem symbolically presents the pearl as the Eucharist.

4.4. BREAD OF LIFE

He compares the unleavened Bread of the Passover as a symbol of the Bread of Life, representing the Eucharist.³⁹ In this way, St. Ephrem has used the Passover celebration to illustrate the parallelism between the Eucharist and the Old Testament unleavened bread.

4.5. PASCHAL LAMB

The paschal mystery is usually understood as the redemption effected by Jesus Christ.⁴⁰ The most important

imagery of the Eucharist used by St. Ephrem is the Paschal Lamb. The Last Supper is the meeting point of the Old Testament Lamb and the True Lamb. It indicates that Eucharist is the continuation of the Last Supper and the sacrifice on the Cross. Therefore, the Eucharistic celebration in the Church makes present the paschal mystery.

5. CONCLUSION

The theological thoughts of St. Ephrem are augmented with imageries, symbols, and metaphors. He extensively used many root metaphors such as a physician, mirror, Medicine of Life, and so on. The employing of imageries familiar to the people has rendered his works more popular as well as poetical. According to Aprem, “In his poetry, St. Ephrem has taken an approach of inquiry to the spiritual reality.”⁴¹ Therefore, he made use of many symbols and imageries to bring out the theology of the Eucharist. His brilliant implementation of the Old Testament imageries to explain the Paschal Mysteries was enough to prove that Jesus continues in the world and gives Himself through the Holy Eucharist. To prove that, he makes use of the imageries like ‘the Coal of Fire’, ‘the Pascal Lamb’, ‘the Pearl’, ‘the Medicine of Life’, and so on and gives a new interpretation. His brilliance in connecting two contradictory ideas is praiseworthy. For Ephrem, there is a connection between incarnation and the Eucharist. He conveys the fact that the Eucharist is the extension of incarnation. The fruit of incarnation is salvation, and that is experienced through the Eucharist.

The proper analysis of the historical background clarifies that the community where he lived was familiar

³⁶ “In Your Bread, Lord, there is hidden the Spirit who is not consumed, in Your Wine there dwells the Fire that is not drunk: The Spirit is in Your Bread, the Fire in Your Wine, a manifest wonder, that our lips have received.” (Faith 10:8) Cf. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 104.

³⁷ Cf. R. Aravackal, “The Glorious Imagery of ‘Pearl’ (*Marganita*) in the Writings of St. Ephrem” in *Ephrem’s Theological Journal* XXV/1&2 (2021) 22.

³⁸ Cf. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 106.

³⁹ “It was the very same Christ in the Upper Room, who gave and was distributed to all.” Cf. S. Brock, *The Luminous Eye: The Spiritual World Vision of Saint Ephrem*, 102.

⁴⁰ G. Francis, “Paschal Promises for a Persecuted People; Eucharistic Perspectives for a Persecuted Church,” in G. Francis (ed.), *Body, Bread, Blood: Eucharistic Perspectives from the Indian Church* (Delhi: Vidyajyoti/ISPCK, 2003) 239.

⁴¹ Aprem, *Mar Aprem, Theologian & Poet*, 68.

with the use of symbols and at the same time the people were influenced by the heretic teachings, as explained. This means that the people were influenced or confused by the false interpretation of the teachings on faith spread by the heretic teachers of the time. To fight against these heretic use of the symbols to interpret divine mysteries, St. Ephrem gives maximum possible clarification to the Catholic teachings on the economy of salvation by incorporating the Old Testament events from the post-resurrection perspective by making use of allusive language. He tried to elevate the faith of the people to the right track. As a zealous missionary, he wanted to protect the faith of the people. Therefore, he used the symbols and imageries familiar to the people and it enabled him to express the actual teachings of the Christian faith. At the same time, it cannot be neglected that the political situation was also not favorable to him in expressing theology directly because Christians were under persecution in the Persian Empire at his time and even later.

This academic paper clarifies that theology is the response of the time to the Faith seeking of the people. Therefore, the language of the theology is decided by the context in which it is introduced. That means all the liturgical or theological language makes a different TL. It is based on how one is exposed to the context. Therefore, the proper knowledge is very significant in the semantic shift (transcendental leap). Thus, the transcendental leap of the imagery is highly dependent on the context as we see in the academic article “An Introduction to the Transcendental Leap.”

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ST. EPHREM'S VISION OF THE MEDICINE OF LIFE

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Abstract: *This academic paper deals with the Ephremian vision of the imagery of the medicine of life. The imagery of the 'Medicine of Life' is one of the critical imageries in the works of St. Ephrem. This imagery is the key by which St. Ephrem attempted to unlock the mystery of salvation through Eucharistic theology. Therefore, a detailed search in the work of St. Ephrem is required to find out how and in what sense the imagery the 'Medicine of Life' is used. The main focus of this academic paper is to study how St. Ephrem has used the imagery to denote the different dimensions of the Eucharist. Therefore, this academic paper also gives special attention to reading each significant event in the Holy Scripture to find out the Eucharistic theology of St. Ephrem.*

Key Words: St Ephrem, Medicine of Life, Eucharistic Imagery, Scripture

1. INTRODUCTION

St. Ephrem has defined the transcendental and transubstantial nature of the Holy Eucharist by using various symbols. The world view of his time might have influenced him a lot in composing poems on divine mysteries by using the full potential of imageries. These epithets were taken from the Scripture and the culture. Human Ascent, the Robe of Glory, the Medicine of Life, the coal of fire, the pearl, the bridal chamber of the heart, and so on are some of the prominent imageries used frequently by St. Ephrem in his hymns, biblical interpretations, and sermons.¹ Among these imageries, the 'Medicine of Life' is vital because he has repeatedly used this imagery to signify the Holy Eucharist. This academic paper focuses on extracting the different dimensions of the Eucharistic imagery of the Medicine of Life used by St. Ephrem in his works. First of all, we will analyze the influences that inspired St. Ephrem to use this imagery and then the different dimensions of it proposed by St. Ephrem to understand the Ephremian vision of the Holy

Eucharist. It will help us to analyze the TL of the imagery in the third academic paper.

2. INFLUENCES ON USE OF THE IMAGERY OF MEDICINE OF LIFE

The use of the imageries is constructive in associating abstract ideas. Since imageries are the subject of human senses and imagination, transferring the transcendental meaning becomes effective. That may be the reason why St. Ephrem has chosen images to interpret the divine realities. He wants to communicate that Jesus Christ, born of the Virgin Mary, suffered, died, and resurrected is the Medicine of Life. And this Medicine of Life is presented in the Holy Eucharist.² St. Ephrem was very good at handling the imageries in his works. To prove that Jesus is the fulfillment of all the prophecies in the Old Testament, he brilliantly uses many incidents from the Old Testament. He uses them as imageries to represent the Holy Eucharist. He says that

¹ Cf. S. Brock, *The Luminous Eye the Spiritual Vision of St Ephrem*, 12.

² "The Grape of mercy was pressed and gave the Medicine of Life to the peoples (Virginity 31:3)." "Our Lord baptized human kind

with the Holy Spirit, He nourished it with the Medicine of Life (Nisibis 46:8)." Cf. Aprem, *Mar Aprem, Theologian & Poet*, 86-87.

Moses had hidden the symbol of Christ as Medicine of Life in the ‘Unleavened Bread (18:15).’³The same concept of the hidden Medicine of Life is also recurring in many of his works, such as ‘Hymns on Nativity’, ‘Virginity’, ‘Paradise’ etc. Now let us see how the culture influenced him to use this imagery.

2.1. CULTURAL INFLUENCE

The search for immortality is there in the minds of all people on earth. Every culture brings its own stories of elixirs that provide immortality. Here we are going to see how the concept of Medicine of Life existed in the culture where St. Ephrem lived. As I stated, medicine is part of the human community. Various types of medicinal practices have existed across the world. There are physical, psychological, and spiritual therapies. These branches have different sub-branches and multiple dimensions by their use. Here, the discussion is on the imagery of Medicine of Life that existed in the Semitic, Egyptian, and Mesopotamian cultures. The reason for focusing on the Middle East terrain is that St. Ephrem was exposed to these three cultures. Among the said cultures, the concept of Medicine of Life is taken from Mesopotamian Culture.

Mesopotamian culture is predominantly based on supernatural concepts, although rudimentary traces of medicine are discernible, whereas, in Greek culture, systematic medical practices existed. It is written in Hammurabi’s Code that if a healer causes a highborn person blindness or death, both hands of the healer will be cut off.⁴ It is to show the concern that was given to medicine and its uses. To be specific, medicine should grant Life and health. It means that even at the time of Babylonian exile, the practice of medicine was there in the Middle East. At the time of St. Ephrem, the medical techniques might have improved. St. Ephrem might have used this medicine concept to present the Eucharistic reality with the imagery of ‘the Medicine of Life.’ That means he made use of the said imagery to expand the meaning of the Eucharist. St. Ephrem has taken the healing aspect of medicine to interpret

the Holy Eucharist. Now we will see the biblical dimensions of the said imagery.

2.2. BIBLICAL INFLUENCE

The hymns and sermons of St. Ephrem were filled with Biblical imageries and symbols. Here we would be analyzing the imageries of Medicine of Life in the light of the Holy Bible. It is helpful to know how the meaning of the cultural product changes with the application of the divine revelation. The Bible is indeed written by using the symbols and imageries of the cultures to which the People of God were exposed. In other words, the human authors of the Sacred Scriptures might have interpreted the divine revelation within the limitations of the human language. Therefore, the gradation of revelation is very evident in the Bible. All the events in the Old Testament are perfected in the New Testament because the New Testament authors have interpreted Old Testament from the Resurrection experience under the guidance of the Holy Spirit.

The imagery of ‘Medicine of Life’ has been directed towards two meanings in the Bible; a) Medicine that gives life and b) Medicine is Life (here the Life is personified). It means that here both ‘medicine’ and ‘Life’ stand for Jesus Christ. The imagery of Medicine of Life is present in the Holy Bible from Genesis to Revelation directly or indirectly. The concept of Medicine of Life is visible in many of the incidents in the Old Testament. Those indirect indications are given below.

- a. **Creation (Gen 1):** Creation is the result of the love of the Triune God. God created the human being in His image and likeness and gave Life, and thereby man participated in the divine Life. St. Ephrem explains it with the imagery of ‘the robe of Glory’ in his ‘Hymn on Paradise’. The story of creation is the recollection of the writer of the Sacred Scripture about the glorious

³ □A. ∴. χ≅ □_≅ Ak□}N □χO} μγ

□≅AX P□ωθ □. ∴. δ} ≅□□≅ □ Cf. J. E. Walters, *Ephrem the Syrian’s Hymns on the Unleavened Bread* (USA: Gorgias Press, 2012) 81.

⁴ Cf. F.P. Retief, and L. Cilliers. “Mesopotamian Medicine,” 3.

state of man. The story of creation conveys the message that the incarnation of Jesus Christ is the result of God's Love towards humanity. The relation between the creator and the creation was a matter of discussion in the 4th century Christian circles. St. Ephrem has used the creation narrative to arrive at the significance of the incarnation, death, and resurrection of Jesus Christ, the Medicine of Life.⁵ Here the aspect of divine love is incorporated in the imagery.

- b. **Sin and Promise** (Gen 3): The fall of man resulted in the loss of the divine Life. Here, God reveals the economy of salvation to humankind that He will send the savior to redeem man from the clutches of the consequences of his great fall and ensure divine life. The aspect of mercy is obvious.⁶
- c. **The Great Flood** (Gen 7): The story of the great flood also deals with a new creation and a level of new life. Here the 'great flood' can broadly be considered 'Medicine of Life' because it purified the society. The concept of purification adds meaning to the imagery.
- d. **Aaron's Miraculous Rod** (Ex 7:8): Aaron's miraculous staff turned into a snake and swallowed all other snakes of the Pharaoh's sorcerers. It also symbolizes Jesus Christ. The miraculous nature of the imagery is emphasized.
- e. **Bread from Heaven** (Ex 16): The Israelites were given bread from heaven, nourishing them with the same. It revitalized them to continue their Exodus. Here also, we can see the indications of the imagery 'the Medicine of Life.' The imagery gets the meaning of the elixir of life.

- f. **Bitter water made sweet** (Ex 15): The people were thirsty, and they were on the verge of death. At this time, the bitter water turned to sweet became an elixir of Life for them. In the physical sense medicine remains bitter when it is received but grants sweetness to life by proving good health and in a spiritual sense it is difficult to follow Christ who is the medicine of life, but He grants eternal joy.
- g. **Water from the Rock** (Ex 17): This was similar to the above-mentioned incident. In this case, also water became a medicine of Life.
- h. **The Decalogue** (Ex 20): The Decalogue was also the Medicine of Life. It consists of the commandment of God. Therefore, the Decalogue is also the Medicine of Life. It stands for the disciplined life in Christ as if a patient arranges his life while in medical treatment. Since Christ is to be received every day, it demands a decorum of life.
- i. **The Blood of the Covenant** (Ex 24): With the blood of the covenant, the Lord made the covenant with Moses. It symbolizes the blood of Jesus upon which the new covenant is established. Therefore, it also stands for the Medicine of Life.
- j. **The Ark of the Covenant** (Ex 25:10-22): The Ark also symbolizes the Medicine of Life, because it stands for the presence of God. It is an archetype of the Church which is the sacrament of Christ.⁷

Here the said incidents from the Bible turned to imageries in the prayers of the people of God later. We will explain how these indirect indications of Medicine of Life are used in St. Ephrem in the succeeding paragraphs. We can see quotes on medicine in Prov 17:22, Jer 30:17, Jer 46:11, Tob

⁵ Aprem, *Mar Aprem, Theologian & Poet*, 35.

⁶ Cf. G. Mathew Kuttilyil, *Eucharist (Qurbana): The Celebration of the Economy of Salvation (Madabranutha)* (Kottayam: OIRSI, 1999) 50-51.

⁷ Cf. A. Nariculam, *Church Liturgy: Towards an Understanding of Catholic Worship* (Aluva: St. Thomas Academy for Research, 2014) 44.

6:5, Sir 6:16. The biblical usages above show that the bible writers have hardly used the primary meaning of ‘medicine,’ whereas its symbolic meanings are prioritized. For example, “Faithful friends are life-saving medicine (Sir 6:16).” Here the ‘faithful friends’ are identified with the ‘life-saving medicine.’ Therefore, the use of the symbolic dimension of a word was prevalent when the Old Testament books were written down.

St. Ephrem uses many Old Testament incidents to substantiate the fact that Jesus Christ fulfills all the prophecies of the Old Testament. His comparative study is not merely confined within the prophecies alone. He takes each incident from the Old Testament and proves logically how Old Testament is perfected in Jesus Christ. He says in “The Hymns on the Unleavened Bread” that those who have eaten from the unleavened bread have demised, whereas the people who received bread from the life-giver attained eternal Life.⁸ He again says that the Church gives the living bread instead of the unleavened given by Egypt. He compared Mary to Eve. According to him, Mary gave humanity the life-giving Bread rather than Eve’s deadly bread. He compares Adam and Jesus as follows:

Let the sixth day praise the one who created Adam on Friday. The evil one deceived him by mixing poison in his food. Whereas Jesus, through His incarnation, dispensed The Medicine of Life to both of them, and thereby man became alive.⁹

The careful analysis of the hymn given above proves that St. Ephrem has made use of all his poetic skills in synthesizing the fall of Adam to justify the incarnation of Jesus Christ. Like this, he makes use of many Old Testament references in his poetical works. He makes it very clear that Jesus is the New Adam who brought salvation to all. Like this, we can see many such references from the Old Testament in the works of St. Ephrem.

⁸ Cf. T. Paniker. “St Ephrem and the Eucharist,” 6.

⁹ G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Manushyavathara Geethangal*, Hymn no 26:9 (Kottaym: OIRSI, 2001) 159.

¹⁰ Cf. J. Maniparambil, *The Gospel According to the Beloved Disciple* (Bangalore: Claretian Publications, 2011) 201.

¹¹ “In Him was life [*zoe*], and the life [*zoe*] was the light of men” (Jn 1:4). John wants to prove that eternal Life resides in the Triune God. We, the humans, become eligible for the divine Life only if

It does not mean that he has not been influenced from the New Testament. His theology is more influenced with the Gospel of St. John. The significance of the Gospel is very vital in understanding the concept of ‘life’ in the imagery of ‘The Medicine of Life.’ St. John has made use of the idea of ‘life’ theologically to present the concept of eternal life, that is, Jesus Christ himself. According to him, Jesus is the resurrection and the Life. “Those who believe in me, even though they die, will live, and everyone who lives and believes in me will never die” (Jn 11:25). It is clear from the quotes that the purpose of the incarnation of Jesus and his death on the Cross is to give Life (Jn 10:11). Life is not a static reality, whereas it is always active in its very nature because the creator of Life is dynamic and active. Life is a ‘language’ through which God speaks. The evangelist’s purpose in writing the Gospel is to give ‘Life’ to the world. (Jn 20:30) This theme is recurring in the works of St. Ephrem. Therefore, the better analysis of the word ‘Life’ in the imagery of the Medicine of Life becomes obvious with the interpretation of *Psuche*, *Bios*, and *Zoe* in St John. All these Greek words are used for denoting ‘Life,’ but with different meanings. For example, *Zoe* means ‘divine life,’ whereas ‘*Psuche*’ means ‘natural life.’¹⁰ Luke also used the word *Bios* for “Life.” (Lk 8:14) The term *Bios* refers to the physical body, whereas Matthew has made use of the word *Psuche* (Mt 16.25). Here Matthew has gone a little ahead of Luke, and we can see a transition of meaning from the body to soul of the humans. When we come to John, it is evident that he has gone to the depth to perfect the concept of “Life” by using the word “*Zoe*” (Jn 1:4). Here he explains how the divine Life was dispensed to the entire humanity through the incarnation and the paschal mysteries of Jesus Christ. He wants to prove that humans get participation in the divine Life in and through Jesus Christ. John has changed the meaning of Life by using the word *Zoe* as ‘life with which God lives¹¹’, ‘life that Father and Son share¹²’, ‘the Son

God wills for the same. Therefore, whoever believes in him may have eternal life. (Jn 3:15)

¹² John again says that eternal Life is shared among the persons in the Trinity. He indirectly proves “*Perichoresis*.” Therefore, God, the Father, willed to send His Son to have eternal Life for humanity who believes in Jesus Christ. “For God so loved the world, that he gave his only Son, that whoever believes in him should not perish but have eternal life [*zoen*]” (Jn 3:16).

Himself is the Life¹³, 'Life gained through faith¹⁴', and 'Life surpasses death¹⁵',

Like St. John, Ephrem tries to prove that only God can impart eternal life to humans. He says that one who believes in Jesus Christ takes part in the divine Life. Therefore, there should take place a kenotic transition to attain eternal life. It is possible only through Jesus Christ. That is why the Eucharistic presence of Jesus Christ is symbolized with the imagery of the Medicine of Life. It means that one has to make a deliberate leap from "Bios" to "Zoe." It happens only when one surrenders one's physical and psychological lives before Jesus by admitting willfully that He is the LIFE. St. Ephrem uses the said imagery in the same line as that of St John. It is clear from the above description that St. Ephrem is highly influenced by the Holy Scripture. His attempt is not to give any refined definition to salvific action of God, but to elevate the minds of the people of God to take part in the mystery of salvation.

2.3. INFLUENCE FROM THE NATURE

Ephrem uses many imageries from nature. He makes use of the name of the objects, animals, plants from nature and composes new imageries. He also quotes all those imageries from the Bible itself. For example, Unleavened Bread, Fountain, Medicine, Fragrance, Goat, Fruit, etc. Here St. Ephrem has brilliantly used these images from nature and provided a shift in the meaning.

¹³ After proving that God and Jesus Christ share the same Life, John teaches the people that "whoever believes in the Son has eternal life [zoen] and whoever does not obey the Son shall not see life [zoen], but the wrath of God remains on him" (Jn 3:36). Then John gives the account of the Samaritan Woman. There Jesus reveals himself to the Samaritan woman that He is the source and summit of eternal life. (Jn 4:14) This account also indicates that salvation is not merely for the Israelites but all the nations.

¹⁴ Then John says that the one who believes in Jesus Christ gains the Life through steady Faith. (Jn 5:24) That is, Peter promises Jesus that he is ready to give his Life for eternal Life. (Jn 6:68) It means that through Jesus, only one can enter into eternal life. (Jn 14:6) Here the encounter with Jesus inspired or, better to say, transformed Peter to lay down his will or soul ('*psyche*') to Jesus.

2. Different Dimensions of the Imagery of Medicine of Life

It is very clear from the previous discussion that Ephrem is highly influenced by the Holy Scripture. Now let us see how St. Ephrem has used the imagery. Here we will discuss the different dimensions of the imagery. This discussion will provide a firm ground to the third academic paper in which the reasons behind the TL of the imagery to the Eucharist are discussed.

3.1. MERCY

St. Ephrem uses the imagery of the Medicine of Life to portray the aspect of Divine Mercy. He says that the fountain of Life was hidden in Jesus, and it was given to all those who search for him.¹⁶ Jesus gave his own body to the people to make them alive eternally.¹⁷ St. Ephrem proves that the Medicine of Life is Jesus Christ himself. The fallen man cannot attain the lost grace by his effort. Therefore, the Second Person in the Trinity incarnated to bring the mercy of the Father to the entire people. It means that the Medicine of Life included the incarnation, passion, death, resurrection, and the second coming of Christ. It means that the eschatological aspect is also included in the term 'Medicine of Life.' Apart from this, the imagery conveys the fact that God is merciful. The incarnation of Jesus Christ is the expression of the Divine Mercy because through Jesus all the people are healed.

3.2. PURIFICATION

St. Ephrem uses the imagery of The Medicine of Life mainly for the Eucharist. But, apart from the same, the said imagery suggests many other meanings related to the

(Jn 15:13) Here, Jesus teaches that the real friend of Jesus will submit the physical Life and the will (soul).

¹⁵ The eternal Life imparted to humans with the power of the Holy Spirit will transcend death. "So Jesus said to them, 'Truly, truly, I say to you, unless you eat the flesh of the Son of Man and drink his blood, you have no life [zoen] in you. Whoever feeds on my flesh and drinks my blood has eternal Life [zoen], and We will raise him on the last day'" (Jn 6:53-54).

¹⁶ "He became thirsty and asked for water. But the fountain of Life that gives life to all was hidden in him. (Translation: Own)" Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 26.

¹⁷ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 28.

Eucharistic effects. One is purification. Medicine purifies the body; likewise, the Medicine of Life sanctifies the soul.¹⁸ Therefore St. Ephrem teaches that the incarnation of Jesus is our purification. His Baptism is the absolution of our sins and His death is our Life.

3.3. TREE OF EDEN

Ephrem makes use of the ‘Tree of Eden’ to bring meaning to the Medicine of Life. He says that man was given a second chance to eat from the ‘Tree of Life’ through the birth, death, and resurrection of Christ.¹⁹ He also says that the dove that Noah sent took a rest in the ‘Tree of Life’ and rejuvenated with new Life.²⁰ He also says that the fruit of the ‘Tree of Life’ symbolizes the Body of Christ (Eucharist), which imparts life to those who eat from it. It means that St. Ephrem uses the ‘Tree of Life’ as the symbol of the Eucharist (or Jesus Christ Himself).²¹ That is why he says that the ‘Tree of Life’ brought hope to the mortals.

3.4. CRUCIFIXION

Medicine of Life and the crucifixion of Jesus are presented interconnected in the poetical works of St. Ephrem. According to him, “Jesus has hidden the eternal life. Therefore, the lifeless death could swallow the One with Life. The fragrance of his life filled in the hades and therefore the hades vomited him.”²² Here Ephrem has presented the death and resurrection of our Lord Jesus. Ephrem says that the Cross in which Jesus was crucified is life-giving, and therefore he continues and says, “The head of the Child upon which the life-giving sign of the cross is marked is blessed!”²³ It indicates Baptism and Confirmation. Through this sacrament, one becomes eligible to receive the Eucharist, the Medicine of Life.

In the ‘Hymns on the Incarnation,’ he explains symbolically how Jesus Christ, the Medicine of Life, was resurrected. He says that in the hades, the death opened its mouth widely and swallowed the body of Jesus, but the

Medicine of Life hidden within the body was sprouted.²⁴ In the Nissibian Hymns, he continues his teachings and explains that the Medicine of Life gave Life to the dead in the hades.²⁵ Therefore, he proves that it is Jesus who gives eternal life.

3.5. BREAD OF LIFE

It is evident in the Gospel of John that the Bread of Life directly indicates Eucharist. Though Ephrem used this Eucharistic imagery separately in his works, he made a brilliant blend of the imageries of the Bread of Life and Medicine of Life. Here the imagery of The Medicine of Life is incorporated in the imagery of the Bread of Life. To explain the same, he takes various incidents from the Old Testament and the New Testament. He makes a symbolic blending to incorporate the said imagery with the imagery of the Bread of Life. And he instructs the faithful how to receive the Eucharist. He says that all those who have eaten from the unleavened bread provided in Egypt died, whereas the life-giving bread, the Medicine of Life, brings Life to everyone who receives it faithfully. And thereby, those people will be rewarded with eternal life.²⁶ Ephrem also warns the people to receive the Bread of Life with the proper disposition of the heart. Otherwise, it will cause eternal separation as if in the case of Judas.²⁷ Here he points out two facts: 1). the unleavened bread received with the proper disposition of the heart in the Holy *Qurbano* is the Medicine of Life and 2). when one receives the Eucharist while being in mortal sin, it becomes a deadly poison to that person.²⁸

Ephrem wants to say that the Eucharist nourishes the body as well as the soul. He also explains the significance of this nourishment. He says that those who are nourished from the bread of life will be taken to heaven and they will see the resurrected Christ.²⁹ Here it is very clear that he gives a kind of eschatological dimension to the Eucharistic Imagery. Since the Eucharist is the medicine for

¹⁸ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 77.

¹⁹ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Kanyathva Geethangal*, Karthrupratheekangal, Hymn no 8:5(Kottaym: OIRSI, 2001) 51.

²⁰ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Kanyathva Geethangal*, 61.

²¹ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Kanyathva Geethangal*, 10.

²² Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 33. (Own Translation)

²³ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Kanyathva Geethangal*, 100.

²⁴ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Manushyavathara Geethangal* (Kottaym: OIRSI, 2001) 41.

²⁵ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Nissibian Geethangal* (Kottaym: OIRSI, 2009) 110.

²⁶ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 36.

²⁷ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 38.

²⁸ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 40.

²⁹ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 36.

eternity, all those who received it with the proper disposition of the heart will be granted participation in the divine life.³⁰

4. CONCLUSION

The tri-cultural influence leads St. Ephrem to use the imagery of the Medicine of Life to bring out the theology of the Eucharist. Since he was moving around biblical imageries, it was easy for the people to comprehend the theology of his writings, particularly that of the Eucharist. He conveys the message that all the revelations of God were fulfilled in Jesus Christ, and the abiding presence of Jesus Christ is continued through the Eucharist.

The imagery of the Medicine of Life is not simple imagery that deals with the physical Life, but rather it goes far beyond its meaning through the poetical works of St. Ephrem. The imagery has been interpreted with existing meaning to elucidate the Eucharist's mystery. He wants to convey that the Eucharist is the actual Medicine of Life and that is Jesus Christ. The application of the imagery of the Medicine of Life has another Eucharistic dimension. That is, the source and means of 'Life' are the same. It means that Christ is the source and Christ is the means. He vividly presents Jesus as the healer and the medicine by which one is granted 'life.' Therefore, the imagery of the Medicine of Life is personified with the Person Jesus Christ.

St. Ephrem makes a lot of comparisons with the Old testament incidents and imageries to convey the message that the people must have widened their thinking horizon in the light of faith to incorporate the mysteries of salvation. He uses all these comparisons to substantiate the fact that participating in the Holy Eucharist is the prefiguration of the *Parousia*. To convey this message, he says, "Whoever has eaten the life-giving bread of the Son will be taken to the heavens to welcome Him."³¹ St. Ephrem brings the eschatological dimension of the Eucharist by using the imagery of the Medicine of Life. He says that when Jesus consecrated the bread and the wine, it became the Medicine of Life to those who receive them with faith.³²

The fall of the first parents caused the forfeiture of the robe of glory. Humanity lost the divine life with this fall, and no one could gain it with one's merit. Therefore, God sends Jesus Christ to this world to grant humanity the participation in the divine life through His salvific action. And whenever we take part in the Holy Eucharist with the proper disposition of the heart, we take part in the divine Life by being in this world that continues after death. St Paul, therefore, reminds us that all who eat and drink without discerning the body, eat and drink judgment against themselves. For this reason, many are weak and ill and some have died (1Cor 11:30-32). If the Eucharist is Christ, then we are partaking in the divine Life through Him, and therefore He is the Medicine of Life. When we live in the grace of God, even after our death, we continue the same. Thus, the Eucharistic interpretation of the particular Judgement reveals that we can partake in the divine life through Jesus Christ. Again, in the universal judgment, we receive the enlightenment that all those who witnessed Jesus Christ directly or indirectly are saved through Him. If the loss of divine Life is death, then gaining Life is nothing but being in Christ. Thus, St. Ephrem wants to convey the same message through the Eucharistic imagery of the Medicine of Life.

This academic paper mainly focused on the different traits of the Eucharistic imagery, the Medicine of Life expressed in the works of St. Ephrem such as mercy, purification, source of Life, and so on. We also analyzed how the culture and the Scripture influenced him in bringing out the Eucharistic theology with the said imagery. In other words, this academic paper explained how the shift of meaning occurs through imageries and symbols. It means that imageries and symbols bring a kind of semantic shift (Transcendental Leap) to liturgical and theological language. This semantic shift is conveyed and appropriately understood only within the context of the text. It means that without getting into the context of the text, it becomes difficult to extract the intended meaning. Here it is very evident from the works of St. Ephrem that the Johannine theology of 'Life' has influenced the theological thinking

³⁰ Cf. B. J. Groeschel – J. Monti, *In the Presence of Our Lord: the History, Theology, and Psychology of Eucharistic Devotion* (Hunting: Our Sunday Visitor Publishing Division, 1996) 63.

³¹ Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 36. (own translation)

³² Cf. G. Chediath, *Mar Aprem: Pesaha Geethangal*, 28.

and writings of St. Ephrem a lot. When the poetical works of St. Ephrem are analyzed within the Johannine spectrum, it becomes evident that the meaning of the said Eucharistic imagery becomes an indicator of the mystery of the economy of salvation too. All the possible semantic shifts of the imagery of the Medicine of Life are analyzed in the next academic paper. It will facilitate to get more qualification of the Eucharist conveyed with the said epithet. The next academic paper will help us to understand the expansion of the transcendental leap.

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